

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№4 (2)

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2026

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, aprel.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqov, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Faxridinov Zafarjon Faxridin o'g'li, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi HIJQKD boshqarma boshlig'i
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Anijon viloyati prokurorining o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi IJQK Departamentining Namangan viloyati boshqarmasi boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamxonovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjayevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Fakhriddinov Zafarjon Fakhriddin ogli, Head of the DCEC under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Rep. of Uzb.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Prosecutor of Anijan Region
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the Namangan Regional Department of the Department of Internal Affairs of Rep. of Uzb.
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

RAQAMLI MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI KORXONALAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	20
Amonov Mirzohid Tuymuratovich, Xodjayev Anvar Rasulovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING BYUDJET MABLAG'LARI HISOBIGA MOLİYALASHTIRILADIGAN LOYIHALARDAGI ISHTIROKINI KUCHAYTIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	26
Maxmudov Rahimjon Hamid o'g'li	
KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI.....	33
Shakirova Gulbaxor Sharipdjanovna	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI VA UNI O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA QO'LLASH IMKONIYATLARI	38
Ne'matova Mavsuma, Xolmamatov Diyorbek	
ВЛИЯНИЕ НАЛОГООБЛОЖЕНИЯ НА ИНВЕСТИЦИОННУЮ АКТИВНОСТЬ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	43
Буранова Лола Вахобовна	
ФИНТЕХ-ЭКОСИСТЕМА КАК ФАКТОР ИНКЛЮЗИВНОГО И УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: СТРУКТУРНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ	54
Эшмуротов Дониёр Ихтиёр угли	
ZAMONAVIY MARKETING KONSEPSIYALARI ASOSIDA XIZMATLAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINING USLUBIY JIHATLARI.....	60
Ostonaqulova Gulsaraxon Matyoqub qizi, Fayzullayeva Zamira Alijonovna	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SERVIS XAVFSIZLIGI INDEKSI: SAMARQAND VILOYATI MISOLIDA	64
Shodmanova Zubayda Ubaydullayevna	
QURILISH FAOLIYATI SOHALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING ILG'OR XORIJIY TAJRIBALARI	
Xusanov Kamoliddin Xolmamat o'g'li	
INSON KAPITALI VA KADRLAR SALOHİYATINI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYALARI	73
Abdullo Sohibov	
O'ZBEKISTONDA URBANIZATSIYA JARAYONLARI JADALLASHUVI VA UNING HUDUDIY XUSUSIYATLARI	84
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich	
KORXONALAR MOLİYAVIY HOLATINI MOLİYAVIY HISOBOTNING XALQARO STANDARTLARI (MHXS) ASOSIDA BAHOLASHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	91
Xamidov Javoxir Shavkat o'g'li	
BIZNES JARAYONLARINI MONITORING QILISH TIZIMINING HOZIRGI HOLATI TAHLILI.....	95
Dadajonova Madina Ravshan qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON VA XORIJIY MAMLAKATLARDA BENEFITSIAR MULKDOR KONSEPSIYASINI QO'LLASHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI	100
Ochilov Farhod Malikovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHNING MAKROIQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH (GDP, BANDLIK VA INVESTITSIYALAR KESIMIDA).....	106
Hayitov Jamshid Xolboyevich	
INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIKKA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI	111
Mamatqulova Hafiza Bahodir qizi	

IPOTEKA BOZORI MUAMMOLARINING EMPERIK TAHLILI VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH STRATEGIYALARI	118
Ollokulova Feruza Mansurovna, Safarova Dilrabo Baxriddin qizi	
MILLIY IQTISODIYOT RAQOBATIDA NAZARIY VA AMALIY QARASHLAR	122
Karimova Iroda Abdusattarovna	
KORPORATIV BANK XIZMATLARIGA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR HAMDA ZAMONAVIY BIZNES MODELLARNI JORIY ETISHNING STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI	128
Qurbonov Abror Abdullayevich	
GREEN ECONOMY DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN AND INDONESIA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY	133
Ibrokhimova Iroda Ikromjon Kizi. Askolani. Javlijev Nuriddin Bektemir o'g'li	
AHOLI BANDLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA REKRUTING AGENTLIKLARINING O'RNI	142
Sherkulova Nodirabegim Baxordin qizi	
ФАКТОРЫ ТЕКУЧЕСТИ КАДРОВ И МЕХАНИЗМЫ УДЕРЖАНИЯ ПЕРСОНАЛА В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	148
Джураева Гузаль Шавкатовна	
BUDJET DAROMADLARI TARKIBIDAGI SOLIQLARNING ULUSHINI BOSHQARISH	156
Abduraxmonova Gulmira Sobir qizi	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA AVTOSERVIS SHOXOBCHALARINI BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	161
Marqayev Xurshid Aliqulovich	
THE ECONOMIC NATURE OF HUMAN CAPITAL AND ITS RECOGNITION IN ACCOUNTING AS AN OBJECT OF ECONOMIC ANALYSIS	165
Zafar Qodirov Abdivaxobovich	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA JARAYONLARINING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH	170
Ibragimov G'ayrat Ablaqulovich. Tursunov Ozod Matlubovich	
Shukurova Nilufar Qahramonova	
IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY	175
Mirzaev Kulmamat Djanzakovich	

IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

Mirzaev Kulmamat Djanzakovich

Head of the Department of Digital Economy,

DSc, Professor at the Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-8558-2455>

e-mail: mirzayevkulmamat@gmail.com

Abstract: This article examines the potential of using digital technologies for innovative development in the service sector. It also analyzes the internal potential for increasing the efficiency of innovative services in the context of our republic's digital economy and provides scientific and practical justification for ways to achieve this.

Keywords: innovative services, digital economy, efficiency of innovative services, digital transformation, artificial intelligence, innovative infrastructure, digital services, IT services, startup, electronic platform, government services.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются возможности использования цифровых технологий для инновационного развития сектора услуг. Также анализируются внутренние возможности повышения эффективности инновационных услуг в условиях цифровой экономики нашей республики и научно и практически обоснованы пути ее повышения.

Ключевые слова: инновационные услуги, цифровая экономика, эффективность инновационных услуг, цифровая трансформация, искусственный интеллект, инновационная инфраструктура, цифровые услуги, ИТ-услуги, стартап, электронная платформа, государственные услуги.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini innovatsion asosda rivojlantirish asosida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari tadqiq etilgan. Shuningdek, respublikamizda raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida innovatsion xizmatlar samaradorligining ichki imkoniyatlari tahlil qilinib, uni oshirish yo'llari ilmiy-amaliy jihatdan asoslangan.

Kalit so'zlar: innovatsion xizmatlar, raqamli iqtisodiyot, innovatsion xizmatlar samaradorligi, raqamli transformatsiya, sun'iy intellekt, innovatsion infratuzilma, raqamli xizmatlar, it-xizmatlar, startup, elektron platforma, davlat xizmatlari.

INTRODUCTION

In the current era of deepening globalization processes in the world economy and rapid development of digital technologies, the issue of developing innovative services and adapting them to the requirements of the digital economy is of particular importance. The service sector, as one of the most dynamic sectors of the economy, plays an important role in ensuring employment and well-being of the population, along with its significant share in the country's gross domestic product. In particular, the fact that the volume of services in Uzbekistan will grow by almost 15 percent in 2025, reaching \$ 82 billion [1], clearly demonstrates the role and importance of this sector in the economy. In recent years, large-scale reforms have been implemented in our republic to develop the service sector on an innovative basis and introduce digital technologies into it. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" sets as an important task "the rapid development of the service sector, increasing its share in GDP, improving the type and quality of services provided to the population" [2]. Also, in 2025, the task is set to "... develop the service sector, in particular, expand high-income types of services such as IT, fintech, consulting, transport and logistics, and increase the services market to more than \$ 100 billion in 2026" [1]. The process of introducing innovative approaches in the service sector and adapting them to the requirements of the digital economy raises a number of scientific and practical problems. In particular, specific criteria for assessing the economic efficiency of innovative services, organizational and economic mechanisms for their digital transformation, as well as the compliance of existing infrastructure and human resources with modern requirements are currently considered relevant areas of scientific research. In particular, the impact of artificial intelligence, "smart" technologies and electronic platforms on the quality of services, their scope and economic efficiency, as well as the possibilities of accelerating these processes, requires separate research.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The level of use of digital technologies predetermines promising directions and stable dynamics of the socio-economic development of the state and society. The features of the development of the modern digital economy as a driving force for the acceleration of economic processes associated with innovations have been studied by many modern researchers, including O.V. Bartyuk [3], J.U. Kambarova [4], A.A. Kisurkin [5], I.L. Kovalyov [6], L.A. Milnikova [7], I.V. Solovyova, L.I. Ushvitsky [8], E.V. Shilova [9] and other authors.

In the conditions of the digital economy, it is precisely through the development of an innovative economy based on knowledge that it is possible to achieve the prospects for economic growth and increase the competitiveness of the state in the world market. Describing the concept of “innovation”, L.A. Milnikova in her scientific works showed that some scientists study “innovation” as a “new input”, others define it as the result of innovative activity, and still others understand it as an investment in innovation.

Innovation is a novelty in the form of the final result of scientific and entrepreneurial activity, interpreted as an investment in a scientific project. Innovations, as an economic category, are considered as a set of knowledge participating in innovation processes, and this, in turn, is the driving force determining technological changes that provide economic benefits and meet the needs of modern society. The role of innovation is constantly growing and is associated with the concepts of innovation, innovation process, innovation potential, and digitalization. This aspect characterizes the presence of elements of action that indicate the dynamics of innovative development.

The implementation of priority innovative development occurs due to the internal innovative potential and the effective influence of management. The innovative development strategy is developed to regulate innovative processes in the state. When developing a specific management influence, it is necessary to take into account the conditions and factors of innovative development of the modern economy.

O.V. Bartyuk noted that in a broad sense, innovative development and economic growth factors should be understood as processes that contribute to a positive change in certain quantitative and qualitative economic indicators.

A.A. Kisurkin's study provides a classification of factors affecting the innovative development of the region, which was obtained by a multi-criteria classification method divided into 12 blocks and assumes the decomposition of all factors depending on their belonging to a particular method in terms of their impact on the object of study. The author identified 75 factors that allow determining the level of innovative development of a country, region or province [5]. The main classification criteria and factors of innovative development are presented in Table 1.

Research Methodology. In the implementation of this study, scientific conclusions were made using the methods of analysis and synthesis, comparison, economic statistical analysis, expert evaluation of scientific research.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

The digital economy is a system that implements production, distribution and consumption processes based on information and communication technologies.

The provision of innovative services in the conditions of the digital economy is a service activity based on new technologies, digital platforms, artificial intelligence, automation, “cloud” computing, fintech, e-commerce and other advanced solutions.

The main characteristics of such services are as follows (fig.1):

Figure 1. Features of innovative service provision in the digital economy

According to the results of the study, the level of innovative service provision in the digital economy in the Republic is determined by assessing its effectiveness. In our opinion, the following criteria are used to assess the effectiveness of innovative services in the digital economy:

- economic efficiency (profitability, profitability, cost reduction);
- social efficiency (employment, service quality, population coverage);
- technological efficiency (level of automation, digitization indicator);
- institutional efficiency (regulatory and legal environment, competitive environment).

In the digital economy, efficiency is measured not only by financial results, but also by the level of satisfaction of consumer needs.

The efficiency of innovative services in the digital economy requires a number of directions of transformation in accordance with digital technologies. These include:

1. Transition to a platform model - services are provided through mobile applications and online platforms (for example, fintech, e-commerce).
2. Data-driven management – using Big Data and artificial intelligence.
3. Remote service provision – telemedicine, online education, remote banking.
4. Automation and robotization – reducing the human factor in service processes.

According to the results of the study, we conducted a comparative analysis of the effectiveness of innovative and digital services to assess the effectiveness of innovative services (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparative analysis of the effectiveness of innovative and digital services

№	<i>Innovative services efficiency</i>	<i>Efficiency indicators</i>
1	IT outsourcing services	Profitability level, export share
2	Fintech services	Transaction speed, operating cost reduction
3	Startup projects	Return on investment (ROI)
4	Consulting and analytical services	Value added
5	Telemedicine	Service coverage, time savings
№	<i>Digital services efficiency</i>	<i>Efficiency indicators</i>
1	Electronic government services	Application processing time, number of users
2	Electronic commerce (e-commerce)	Sales volume, conversion rate
3	Online education (EdTech)	Coverage level, course completion percentage
4	Digital banking services	Transaction number, cost reduction
5	Cloud services (Cloud)	IT cost savings

As the table shows, innovative services are a significant driver of economic growth. They are characterized by high profitability, export potential, and the creation of new jobs. Digital services, in turn, improve operational efficiency across all sectors of the economy, reduce transaction costs, and ensure governance transparency. In the future, the integration of these two areas—that is, the large-scale implementation of innovative ideas through digital platforms—will ensure the sustainable development of the services sector. In particular, thanks to the development of e-commerce, fintech, and cloud technologies, Uzbekistan will have the opportunity to increase service exports and expand the share of the digital economy.

The development of Uzbekistan's e-government system, the expansion of the unified government services portal, and digital payment systems contribute to the increased effectiveness of innovative services.

Digital services, in turn, enhance the effectiveness of innovative services. Based on the results of the analysis conducted as part of the study, a number of factors influencing the development and increased effectiveness of innovative services in the digital economy were identified. We believe these include:

- Technological infrastructure for service delivery (internet speed, mobile coverage, servers and data centers);
- Human resources for service delivery (IT specialists, startup ecosystem);
- Investment environment for service delivery (venture capital, government grants);
- Regulatory framework for service delivery (digital signatures, data protection legislation);
- Presence of a competitive environment in the services sector, etc.

The influence of such factors is particularly significant in our Republic, expanding opportunities for supporting innovative startups, developing export-oriented IT services, and attracting foreign investors (investments).

Based on the analysis results, the following strategic areas for the development of innovative services in the digital economy in our Republic were identified, creating opportunities for increasing the economic efficiency

of the sector. These include:

1. Developing a digital transformation strategy in the services sector—a customized digitalization model for each service provider.
2. Expanding the startup ecosystem for the implementation of innovative services—developing incubation and acceleration programs.
3. Modernizing the training system in the services sector—expanding IT and digital business programs in higher education institutions.
4. Developing public-private partnership (PPP) mechanisms in the services sector.
5. Ensuring digital security in the services sector—strengthening the cybersecurity system, etc.

Conclusions and suggestions. Based on the results of the study, in our opinion, to improve the effectiveness of innovative services in the digital economy, it is advisable to implement the following:

- first, prioritizing criteria for evaluating innovative services suitable for the digital economy, especially in terms of achieving economic, social, and technological efficiency;
- second, systematically implementing the transformation of innovative services and the widespread use of a number of modern digital economy technologies, namely artificial intelligence, big data, etc. — Third, a number of factors increase the effectiveness of innovative services development in the digital economy, including technological infrastructure, human resources, the development of an investment climate, the availability of a regulatory framework, and the creation of a digital environment conducive to innovative services;
- Fourth, ensuring the effectiveness of innovative services in the digital economy requires identifying important strategic areas for the sector's development, namely, digital transformation strategies, expanding the startup ecosystem, ensuring digital security, and others.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning Oliy Majlis va O'zbekiston xalqiga Murojaatnomasi. – Toshkent, 26-dekabr 2025-yil. – URL: https://uza.uz/oz/posts/joriy-yilning-ozida-xizmatlar-hajmi-qariyb-15-foizga-osib-82-milliard-dollariga-yetdi_800798
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 28.01.2022-yildagi “2022–2026-yillarga mo'ljallangan Yangi O'zbekistonning Taraqqiyot strategiyasi to'g'risida”gi Farmoni, PF-60-son.
3. Бартюк О.В. Факторы инновационного экономического роста России [Электронный ресурс] // Интернет-журнал «Науковедение». – 2014. – № 6. – URL: <http://naukovedenie.ru/PDF/65PVN614.pdf>
4. Камбарова Ж.У. SWOT-анализ современного состояния национальной инновационной системы Кыргызской Республики в условиях Евразийского экономического союза (ЕАЭС) // Экономический вестник. – 2018. – № 3. – С. 15–17.
5. Кисуркин А.А. Факторы, влияющие на инновационное развитие региона, и их классификация по уровням управления // Современные проблемы науки и образования. – 2012. – № 2.
6. Ковалев И.Л. Цифровая трансформация как катализатор инновационных процессов в экономике // Большая Евразия: развитие, безопасность, сотрудничество. – 2019. – № 2-1. – С. 374–380.
7. Мыльникова Л.А. Инновации и цифровизация российской экономики // Экономический журнал. – 2019. – № 1 (53). – С. 107–119.
8. Ушвицкий Л.И., Тер-Григорьянц А.А., Соловьева И.В. Факторы и условия инновационного развития экономики // Мир науки, культуры, образования. – 2014. – № 6 (49). – С. 271–276.
9. • Шилова Е.В., Дьяков А.Р. О феномене четвертой промышленной революции и его влиянии на экономику и управление // Вестник Прикамского социального института. – 2018. – № 3 (81). – С. 86–95.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2026. № 4 (2)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>